

Art and Craft in Proverbs: Metaphor in Meitei Cultural Life

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Abstract: *The paper tries to examine the socio-cultural and economic life of Meitei community of Manipur from the underlying perspectives of proverbs concerning art and craft based on the folklore studies. The production and consumption of art and craft has tied up within the socio-cultural activities of the people. The art and craft made for different purposes has both tangible and intangible dimensions. It is a cultural symbol that reveals their communal perception, worldview, belief systems, norms and values of the community in secular and sacred life. Proverb, which are short and concise sentences in the form of verbal art are used by the Meiteis as part of a communicative system since the past generation to reveal their communal identity and knowledge system. Since the proverb used as verbal art form in the folklife of Meitei community has been used from the past generation as communicative system reveals communal identity and knowledge system. Proverbs used in Meitei Community incorporate the technology and typology of the art and craft in different ways of expression as metaphor, symbol etc. showing various perspectives in socio-cultural and economic life.*

Key words: *Art and Craft, Cultural Life, Metaphor, Proverb.*

Introduction:

Culture is a composite form of various aspects of human behavior that includes oral narratives, material cultures, beliefs, religious practices, customary laws etc. It is inherited and transmitted orally through generation to generation. Geography and environment of a particular community is one of the factors that enhance their unique cultural life (including both verbal and non-verbal expressive behaviors). It helps the community to maintain their various socio-political norms and values by sharing their understanding and experiences from their surrounding environment. Sharing of such expressive cultural behaviors becomes an essential component of their cultural life. These inherent expressive behaviors become a symbol of their unique cultural identity that differentiates them from others.

The distinctiveness of the cultural life of any community echoes in their art and crafts that are used in their mundane life. Generally, art and craft deal with the production and consumption of artifacts that are used in various context of socio-economic and political life. The types of products of art and craft and their methods/processes of production are linked with established symbolical social meaning and values. Such symbolic meanings and values correlate with domestic and social life in terms of age, gender, time, work and leisure. These are expressed through customs and practices. Art and craft is not only a product that boosts the economy, but also the attachment of socio-cultural values and norms make it diverse. As Irfan Habib has commented that the consumption is more than an economic process; in fact, it is actually context-based. The symbolic meaning of the craft work depends on the context. The products of art and craft are used in different ways - as household wares, as gift items, as a symbol for establishing relationship between members of family or a society, as an item in social conventions and as an item in ritual practices (Habib, 2008: 650-1750). An artifact has the ability to signify or establish not only social meaning but also sub-cultural affinity, occupation, leisure activity and social status. Moreover, an individual does not use object on his/her own wish but in relation to other individuals within inter or intra-group and space-time context. It is an object which is used as a symbol that represents the identity of the group (Woodward, 2007: 3-10). In fact, artifacts and their functions are the manifestation of their worldviews that are perceived and conceived. The production and consumption of art and craft become cultural expressive behaviors within a core of socio-cultural life of the folk.

Like other communities, Meitei community also rich not only in art and craft, but also in those different traditional expressive behaviors. Folk culture of Meitei community has diverse features that demonstrate their integrated socio-cultural life. There are various components including techniques in creating art and craft, myth, legend, folktale, song, riddle, and proverb are transmitted verbally from one generation to another. These components cover all social life, activities, beliefs, mystery, cosmology, myths and legends that reflect ethical values from their perception to show their unique identity. These components are used in various cultural activities in day-to-day life as agent to share, to interact and to communicate each other. Generally, community members use oral narratives as a cultural metaphor in their domestic as well as in public sphere. It is narrated orally to offer a sense of morality, attitude, behaviour, livelihood which are pictured to be transposed to the social situation. Generally, in Meitei Community these oral narratives are expressed orally in small or large gathering for amusement or for conveying social identity, ethnicity, wisdom, cultural knowledge, morality, worldview etc. Proverbs are one of them.

In proverbs, metaphorical words are generally used. Among the cultural expressive behaviors, proverb is also one of the verbal art form used by the people to educate the young or to make a statement strong and precise. Etymologically, proverb is known as *Paorou* which is made by combining two words – *Pao* = news or information or statement, and *Rou/lou* = to accept, that means acceptable statement/information. It concisely conveys different meanings in various

contexts. The contextual meanings of proverbs express socio-cultural aspects of life and socio-cultural values (Firth, 1926: 134-153). Roger D. Abrahams (1968: 150) says that “Proverbs are traditional answers to recurrent ethical problems; they provide an argument for a course of action which conforms to community values. They arise in the midst of a conversation, and are used by speakers to give a ‘name’ to the ethical problem confronting them, and to suggest ways in which it has been solved in the past (though the suggestion is not necessarily directed immediately to the ones confronted by the problem).” Moreover, proverbs condense stories in metaphoric way in conversational context. Therefore, proverb is used as an impersonal vehicle for personal communication. When a proverb is used in a suitable context, it may serve as a perfect communicative agent. Since cultural norms, values and belief systems of the community are mirrored through their proverbs, the art and craft as a metaphor of the society are used in the proverbial expression. For the first time, A. J. Primrose (1888) in the Manipuri Grammar, Vocabulary, and Phrase Book, produces some Manipuri proverbs to give an idea of the style and composition from linguistic view. J. Shakespear (1911) describes cultural meaning through translating the collected Manipuri proverbs. Manipuri philosopher M.K. Singh (1993) and folklorist Oinam Ibochouba Singh (1993) had worked on the folklore of Meitei community highlighting the aspects of theories and methodology for understanding oral tradition. Loitongbam Birjita Devi (2007) attempts to describe significances and distinguish the types of proverbs that reflect the various aspect of Meitei socio-cultural life. M. M. Ahmed and P. K. Singh (Arvind Kumar, 2008: 179-185) study on Manipuri proverbs having reference to plants that explain significance of plants with human nature, human way of life especially for food and shelter. From the literature survey, proverbs concerning art and craft based on the folklore studies have not studied to highlight the significance of material culture. The cultural symbolism inherent and inbuilt in art and craft connected to them were not articulated to the crafter and people who used it. Therefore, the present article is an effort to analyze one of the folkloric genres known as proverbs spoken in Meitei language among the Meitei people of Manipur. The paper also tries to look at the importance of their art and crafts as well as socio-cultural structure of the community.

The present article is descriptive in nature and result of both primary and secondary data. For the primary sources, researcher has conducted an intense field visit applying interview and group discussion method. The primary data is an outcome of the ethnographic study conducted in Andro village and Wangkhei of Imphal East dist., Langmeidong, Laimanai and Thongjao village of Kakching dist., and Utlou village of Bishnupur dist. Present article is a product of researcher’s field work experiences during his doctoral research. Period for the fieldwork was carried out in different stages from July 2015 to September 2017.

Meitei Community – A Brief Introduction:

Manipur¹, a Northeastern state of India, is a land of diversity. People here belong to diverse ethnic, linguistic, cultural and religious groups. People of the state speak Kuki-Chin and Tibeto-

Burman group of language. The communities of the people who are living in this state are Meitei², Brahman, Pangal, Naga, Kuki and other groups. Among these ethnic groups, Meitei community can be divided into three groups - Meitei/Meetei, Meitei Bamon (Brahman) and Loi³. All the Meitei, Meitei Bamon (Brahman) and Pangal (Muslim) are majorly settled in the valley which is in the central plain area of the state. The tribes and ethnic groups as cited above, living in this valley and hill engage in the professions of handloom, basketry and pottery production from time immemorial. Each group has their own unique art and craft in a distinctive physical structure for different purposes made by using their raw materials and techniques learnt from their past generation.

From the historical records and oral narratives, it is known that Meitei community was formed by integrating various social groups or tribes which were guided by their territorial principle. The formation of Meitei community had started under the political power of Meidingu Nongda Lairen Pakhangba in 33 A.D. Even the formation of Meitei as a united group was not happened in one period. However, the system of clan principality and division of people among the clan was precipitated as a social and political system. Each clan has their own autonomous principality and government in their respective territory. The matrimonial alliances between the clans and sharing of one political system under the feudal power of Mangang/Ningthouja clan made them to form as one cultural group. So, a composite culture has been developed by amalgamating all the cultural norms, custom, language and material culture of each clan/group and has been legitimized under one political power, identifying Meitei community as a one homogenous group. The worldview and perception of Meitei community is reflected through their verbal and non-verbal expressive behaviors constructed with a deep belief system associated with inhibited geographical region, socio-political and economic life. The cultural beliefs and practices of Meitei community are associated in polytheistic, animistic and naturalistic form. The veneration towards their deities and various beliefs and practices has been significantly manifested in the cultural and social sphere of Meitei identity. Moreover, the art and craft of Meitei community is used for cultural symbol that represent their profane and sacred life. Their art and craft becomes an important agent in order to recognize the individual identity and the common Meitei identity in various contexts.

As Meitei people inhabits in the valley region of Manipur, the surrounding environment leads the members of the community to adopt various occupations like fishing, weaving, basketry, pottery etc., other than agriculture. The products manufactured from such occupation are being utilized as a medium of exchange/ barter/ gift/ share to bring solidarity and cohesion intact among the people of the community. However, engagement of an occupation or division of labour among the people is based on their gender, class, age and social status. The production and consumption of art and craft in socio-economic life in Meitei community has been a part of their cultural life and are done as per norms, values, belief systems of the community.

The study on the art and craft of Meitei people is truly an important genre as the uses of these products are not only for the utility and consumption purpose, but also the attachment of various socio-religious beliefs and practices makes them unique and multifaceted. In their socio-religious life, art and craft are mostly related with various folkloric genres like myth, tales, proverbs, narratives etc. and mostly related with the supernatural entities. Through these verbal expressions, they are connected with each other and bound them with a sense of unity. The art and crafts are also become an important tool to represent various supernatural entities in their daily as well as in the ritual life. Theoretically, structuralism and semiotics are very suitable for interpretation of art and craft in the cultural contexts of Meitei community. It is because artifacts and skill that is depicted in their production is nothing than a language of sign or symbols of the community having socio-cultural meaning attributed by the community. Existence of various expressive behavioral acts in their various personal as well as communal rituals, various belief systems will open definitely help to understand the structure, function and worldview of the community. Therefore, the significance of the present study is related to categories of art and craft in their mundane life. Furthermore, analysing proverbs will also help to understand its symbolic and structural uses as a metaphor in their socio-cultural life.

Art and Craft in Proverbs:

Metaphors in proverbs are indices of attitude and socio-cultural life. The metaphorical elements are analogue with the social structure, norms, values, social status, and socio-cultural practices. The thought and philosophy attached to art and craft of a particular group is explicitly or implicitly expressed in proverbs. Moreover, art and craft used in proverb are based on experience of people indicating wisdom for finding a solution. In such proverb, cultural behavior associated with material culture of the community is depicted even if it is expressed metaphorically. Such proverbs using art and craft suggest probable results/consequences helping to illuminate the way out of problems. Proverbs serves as an impersonal vehicle for personal communication to communicate and integrate within the community. So, it gives knowledge and educates the folk and also controls the villages, family, and community.⁴ The paper deals with how the socio-cultural and economic life of the community is reflected in the art and craft based on proverbs. Depending on the types of art and craft used, the proverbs of the Meiteis may be classified into three categories- proverbs having metaphorical elements of weaving, basketry, and pottery.

1) Proverbs Having Metaphorical Elements of Weaving:

In Meitei community, weaving is a gender based occupation. Traditionally, it is one of the main occupations of womenfolk. As a tradition, every mother trained her daughters the art of weaving and spinning. Expert weavers are considered as a symbol of pride and essential quality of an ideal woman. Use of work culture and technology of weaving in proverbs can be analysed in different ways to know their socio-economic life. For instance, there is a proverb- *Kari Una Saba Tarengno, Sin-changde, Sin-kaore*- “Which timber is used to make this spinning wheel /

it has been low in mood / it has almost forgotten how to spin”. This proverb shows that spinning wheel is used in weaving by the Meitei community. In this proverb spinning wheel is used as a metaphor within womenfolk in the sense that the poor workwoman blames her tools. There is another proverb *Sagol mamang Punjao pubi nungshit mamang Huitri kappi*- “the woman who’s carrying big pot in front of the horse / the woman who’s carding cotton against the wind”. The proverb shows the technique of carding of cotton fibre using *Huitri* (cotton-bow; carder) in weaving and carrying of water in big pot by womenfolk of Meitei Community. This proverb reveals the associated material and the type of activity engaged by womenfolk in their household activities. It is an ironical statement expressing unwise futile effort of someone.

Meiteis are the followers of their traditional religious practices as well as Vaishnavite Hinduism. They also venerate their ancestors. The cloths used by ancestors were kept in *Tabu*, a bamboo basket with lid. Preservation of ancestral clothes and precious things shows not only their practice of ancestor veneration but also the preservation of the memory of family ancestor and progenitors. Moreover, the sacred cloth which is used in the ritual purpose is preserved for the family, *Sagei*⁵ and village. There is also the belief that preservation of ancestral garments will protect the family by keeping off evil spirits. Such belief system practices by them can be seen from the proverb like- *Tabunungda thamba Charei thupchinbagum mangaire*- “Like keeping cloths in piles inside a bamboo basket”. The basket *Tabu* is usually used as a safe custody for *Charei* (cloth) or other precious items. Use of bamboo-made baskets can also be traced from this proverb. Among Meitei community, systematic folding of a cloth and wearing of the cloth which has folded impression is considered a luxury. In ritual, folding into three part of a cloth is profoundly embedded. It represents three levels of perceptual world viz. sky, earth and underworld. So, keeping a well folded cloth in an old traditional basket reveals their cultural values and activities. However, this statement expresses when a thing is kept that does not serve the actual purpose.

2) Proverbs Having Metaphorical Elements of Pottery:

Like weaving, pottery is also gender-based occupation of womenfolk. But, it specifically belongs to womenfolk of *Loi*, specially *Chakpa*⁶, a group of Meitei Community. This monopolized and ethnic based-occupation which shows their ethnic identity is incorporated in proverbial expression as a cultural metaphor. *Thoubandong Khut-naibina Nganthakpu Chaphu Mapalla Hang-ngee?*- is a popular proverb of the community, which etymologically refers to- “The potter of *Thoubandong* village asks whether the *Nganthak* (smoking pipe) is a bud of *Chaphu* (pot)”. Here, *Nganthak* is compared with a bud of flower and *Chaphu* with a full blossom flower. The proverb implicitly says that a person intentionally try to hide her previous social identity when she married from a lower social group to a higher social group. It proves craftsmanship of women and vertical social mobility of women in the community. The proverb is originated from a remark of a queen whose maternal family belongs to a pottery community. The proverb- *Chairen Chaphu kainaba yeiba nate* literally means “Are the *Chairen* pots beaten

to break them?” The proverb shows *Chairen* is a potter village and they use the technique of paddle-and-anvil. As pots are beaten with a paddle to shape them discipline is necessary for good upbringing of a child as similar with the English proverb “Spare the rod and spoil the child.” In their sacred and profane life, pot is used in various purposes- utility and conceptual. It is used for veneration of goddess. Every potter makes their pot in a perceptual structure of human being classifying various parts of the body such as mouth, neck, abdomen and buttock. The process of making pot from the molding of clay to final shaping of a pot is used as metaphor of giving birth to a child. Meitei people considers their parents as living gods. The words of the elders are considered weightier than the words of the expertise of the younger generations. It is expressed in the proverb- *Ahan mathina chaphu melli*- “Feces of the elders mend the cracked pot”. It is expressed when young people get into trouble neglecting the advice of elders. Here, the feces are metaphorically used as precious advice of the elders which is helpful to decrease the mistakes of the younger generations, metaphorically, a cracked pot. It shows hierarchical structure of a family in the socio-economic life of the Meitei Community.

Schadenfreude is expressed in the proverb *Chaphu kairaga kwakna harao ee* means “Breaking of pot makes crow happy”. Culturally, a cooking pot or *chaphu* also represents a family or lineage and when a family member or a member of an extended family dies cooking pots are ritualistically destroyed and replaced them with new cooking pot. So, in this proverb breaking a pot is metaphorically used to convey misfortune of others and the crow or dog represents those who feel pleasure and joy seeing other’s misfortune. An earthen pot also represents the cultural knowledge and wisdom of a person. It is shown in the proverb like *Houdong tumin leibana Chaphu ngammi*- “A quite cat steals fish from your fish-bowl” and *Thandaba Chaphu makhol thok-ee*- “Empty or half-filled pots make the most noise”. The first proverb expresses that a wise man usually remains silent and carries out his work successfully whereas the second proverb conveys the idea that those person with the lease knowledge are generally talkative. Fishes are generally stored in a fish- earthen pot to keep away from cats. But a silent and wise cat can easily steal the fish. Here cat is used as an analogy to a wise man.

3) Proverbs Having Metaphorical Elements of Basketry:

Basketry is one of the common occupations of those who are retired from heavy agricultural work. Like other, baskets are used as metaphors in various proverbs to define the perception of the community. Among different types of basket, *Sangbai* and *Laitang* basket are usually found in proverbs. These are standard baskets used in measuring dry commodities, as paddy or grain. For instance one *Sangbai* (around 32 seers) is equal to four *Laitang* baskets. The proverb “*Kok Sangbai ama, Lousing laitang ama*” which literally means “Head as big as *Sangbai* and intellectual capacity as small as *Laitang*” is analogy of a person who in foolish pride believes himself wise enough. It is also used when someone dream a lot without any action. In another proverb, the measuring baskets are also metaphorically used as the degree of one’s effort in life

and its fruit. The proverb- *Awaba Sangbai nungaiba Laitang* which literally means “the amount of sorrow is *Sangbai* and that of happiness is about as much as *Laitang*” is used when a person is less rewarded than he or she expected. In that case, the proverb is used to imply that human life is largely full of hardships and the happiness is short-lived.

Sangbai is again found in other proverb *Tumai sangbai ama charingeida macha tara pokpa* which literally means “Giving birth of ten children while having one full *Sangbai* of grain”. It refers to those who enjoy life extravagantly with limited wealth without thinking for future. Here, *Tumai Sangbai Ama-* one full *Sangbai* of grain is metaphorically used as limited wealth of a person and *Macha Tara Pokpa-* giving birth to ten children is metaphorically used as enjoying life extravagantly.

Art and craft used by the community is also used in proverbs for showing their economical livelihood. *Nga Tungol amana, phou Sangpai amana Icha chaokhiba nate* which means “My child is not brought up by feeding just one *Tungol* (fishing basket) of fish and one *Sangbai* of rice”. The proverb shows that the responsibilities and task of parent for bringing up of a child is not an easy and single task and they struggle a lots with much energy and time. Rice being the staple food and fishing an occupation of the community are shown in the proverb. In proverb *Namma hairingeida yadraga Pabot lollaga yaba-* which means “Not agreed while asking for carrying *Namma*/single lot/burden but agreed when situation compel to carry *Pabot*/double lots/burden” signifies one’s ignorance/negligence while asking for doing an easier work but unavoidable acceptance when situation compel him/her to do more difficult work. Use of two hanging hooked baskets in pair with a bar for carrying loads of articles/things on the shoulder by the community is also known from the proverb. It is used to advise that negligence while a work being easier will result in compulsion for carrying out the work when it becomes difficult.

Conclusion:

From the above discussion the mode of production and use of art and craft in their life are used as metaphor or symbol for conveying a message/idea/information in social and domestic life. The nature and features of art and craft in the production and consumption are compared with the life of individuals/group of people in the community. So, the art and craft are lively in expression and use of art and craft in proverbs in metaphoric way shows a connection between the life of the community and their art and crafts. The material culture and work culture are shown in the proverbs of the community. Besides, social norms, convention, social structure and belief system are also reflected in the mode of using art and craft in the proverbs, retracing the past socio-cultural and economic life. Explicitly and implicitly, art and craft used as metaphors in their proverbs is the mirror of their attitude and socio-cultural life. So, Meitei’s art and craft is analogue to the social structure, norms, values, social status and socio-cultural practices. Moreover, thought and philosophy, wisdom and knowledge of their community are vividly expressed. As a tradition, their proverbs are taught

by the elder to the younger not only for continuing cultural values and norms but also for development of perception of art and craft that reflects gender identity, occupation, socio-cultural activities, moral and wisdom of the society. ♦♦

Notes:

1. R. B. Pemberton mentions that the term ‘Manipur’ was coined during 18th century when the Meetei converted to Vaishnavism. It was named as Kangleipak, Meitrepak etc. The land which is inhabited by the Manipuri was known by different names by the neighboring countries. The Burmahs call it Kathe; Cachar names it Moglie; Assamese calls it Meklee and Cassay knows it by the Shans. In *The Eastern Frontier of India*, R. B. Pemberton, New Delhi: Mittal Publication, 1835, (reproduced again in 2005), pp.19-20.
2. Captain Pemberton concludes that Meetei are descendants from a Tarta Colony from China. Further, T.C. Hodson mentions that Meetei are the group who came from South West of China and scattered throughout the central part of Manipur. The name ‘Meitei’ has been derived from the word mee - man, and thei – separated. In *The Meitheis*, T. C. Hodson, Delhi: B. R. Publishing Corporation. (Reprinted), 1975, p. 10.
3. “Loi are a distinct group of people in Manipur who speak Chakpa (which is a dialect of the Meitei) and worship Koubru, Panam Ningthou, and Kounu. Their traditional occupations are distillation of liquor, rearing of pigs, silkworm farming and pottery making. They were included in the list of scheduled castes in the year 1956.” In *People of India Manipur*, K.S. Singh, Anthropological Survey of India, Calcutta, 1998, p. 110.
4. William R. Bascom, “Folklore and Anthropology”, *Journal of American Folklore*, Vol. 66 (1953), p. 290; see also William R. Bascom, “Four Function of Folklore” in Alan Dundes (ed.) *The Study of Folklore*, 1965, p. 295
5. Sagei is an extended-family.
6. Chakpa are group of people who were believed to be lived from the Chak/Sak period before the reign of Nongda Lairen Pakhangba. They were treated as lower group because of their non-acceptance of Vaishnavism and their accompanied occupations- pottery, silk rearing, blacksmith, etc. were also considered as lower.

References:

- ♦ Boivin, N. *Material Cultures, Material Minds: The Impact of Things on Human Thought, Society, and Evolution*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2008
- ♦ Brown, R. *Statistical Account of Manipur*. New Delhi: K. M. Mittal Sanskaran Prakashak (reprinted), 1975
- ♦ D. Abrahams, R. “Introductory Remarks to a Rhetorical Theory of Folklore”. *The Journal of American Folklore*, 81.320 (1968): 150
- ♦ Dorson, R. M. (Ed.) *Folklore and folklife: An Introduction*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1972
- ♦ Dundes, A., & Arewa, E. O. *Proverbs and the Ethnography of Speaking Folklore*. *American Anthropologist*, 66.6 (1964): 70-85
- ♦ Dundes, A. *Folklore Matters*. Knoxville: The University of Tennessee Press, 1989
- ♦ *Interpreting Folklore*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1980
- ♦ Firth, R. “Proverbs in Native Life, with Special Reference to Those of the Maori. *Folklore*”, 37.2 (1926): 134-153. <http://www.jstore.org/stable/1255686>, accessed on 28-03-2017
- ♦ Hudson, T.C. *The Meitheis*. Delhi: B. R. Publishing Corporation (Reprinted), 1975
- ♦ Singh, L. I. *Introduction to Manipur*. Imphal: Friends Union Press (2nd edition), 1963
- ♦ Shakespear, J. “Manipuri Proverbs”. *Folklore*, 22.4 (1911): 473-475
- ♦ Kabui, G. *History of Manipur*, vol.1. New Delhi: National Publishing House (Third edition), 2011
- ♦ Mieder, W. *Proverbs: A Handbook*, London: Greenwood press, 2004
- ♦ Pemberton, R. B. *Report on the Eastern Frontier of British India*. Calcutta: Baptist Mission press, 1835
- ♦ Bascom, W. R. *Folklore and Anthropology*. *The Journal of American Folklore*, 66.262 (1953): 283-290
- ♦ (1954). *Four Function of Folklore*. *The Journal of American Folklore*, 67.266 (1954): 333-349
- ♦ Primrose, A. J. *Manipuri Grammar, Vocabulary, and Phrase Book, Some Manipuri Proverbs*, The Assam Secretariat Press, 1888
- ♦ Singh, M. K. *Folk Culture of Manipur*. Delhi: Manas Publication, 1993
- ♦ Kumar, A. (Ed.) *Environmental Science: Appreciation and Perception*. Daya Publishing House, 2008
- ♦ Devi, L. B. *Manipuri Paorou Neinaba*. Imphal: Palace Compound, 2007
- ♦ Singh, O. I. *Folklore Bigyan*. Nepen Institute of Manipuri Folklore (Third edition), 2010
- ♦ Singh, K.S. *People of India Manipur*, Calcutta: Anthropological Survey of India, 1998